

A STUDY ON THE PROSPECTS AND PROBLEMS OF UNORGANISED LABOURS IN INDIA

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Abstract:

India comprises 43.7 crore people working with the skill in the residual sector as unorganized labours. Around 24.6 crore engage in agriculture, 4.4 crore in construction and remaining people in the manufacturing and service sectors. This sector faces eventual deficiencies in regulations over employment, remuneration pattern, poor employer and employee relationship and casual work culture. Informal sector covers large number of workers from rural and substantial number from the urban areas by potentially engaging family labour and technology. The unorganized labours engage in casual, seasonal and scattered employments, which are not unionized. A large number of statutes addressing issues concerning unorganized sector are neither feasible nor practicable. Unorganised workers are also kept away from the Social Security Benefits such as Old Age Pensions, Gratuity, Employees State Insurance, Workmen's Compensation etc. in India. Unorganized sector plays pivotal role in the development of Indian economy. For the effective implementation of labour legislations for the informal sectors, it is essential to study the existing employment relations, after analyzing the existing working conditions of unorganized labours in India should be given special attention. This paper examine about factors influencing employment in this unorganized sector, types of employments, regulatory protections, contribution to Indian economy and challenges faced by the unorganised workers. It tries to suggest measures to overcome the obstacles in the unorganised sector by ensuring physical, economic and intellectual wellbeing of the unorganized labours.

Index Terms: Workers, Unorganized Sector, Deficiencies, Economy & Wellbeing

1. Introduction:

According to Unorganised Workers Social Security Act, 2008 'Unorganised Sector' means an enterprise owned by individuals or self employed workers, engaging in production or sale of goods or service employing less than ten employees. Kanak Kanthi Bagchi and Nirupam Gobi (2012) British economist Keith Hart introduced the term 'informal sector' in 1971. The unorganised sector, comprises, informal workforce with low working status and poor laws and regulations enforced by the government. Tiwari R.S. (2002) in 1970s, International Labour Organisation introduced World Employment Programme Mission in Kenya, Columbia, Srilanka and Philippines to encourage employment in informal sectors to bring economic growth. This initiation has brought attention of the world towards unorganized sector. Second National Commission on Labour (2002) informal sector comprises large number of rural workforce and substantial urban workforce, potentially using family labour and technology. The unorganized are engaged in casual, seasonal and scattered employments which prevents them to be unionized. The sector even marked with low incomes, unstable employments and lack of protection from legislation and trade union. Section 2(m) of the unorganised Workers' Social Security Act, 2008 defines Unorganised worker as either home-based, self employed, work for wage in the unorganised sector or working in the organised sector which is not covered under any acts specified in the schedule II of the Act. National Commission for Enterprises in the Unorganised Sector (2007) only 0.4 per cent unorganized workers were availed with the facility of Provident fund during 1999 to 2000. Kishore CSamal (2013) in a study of urban Ghana, rural migrants, entering the urban labour market were lacking in the skills and experience to work in the urban formal sectors, hence, they were forced to work in informal sectors. The National Commission on Labour listed the categories of unorganized labours including Contract labours working in the construction sector, Casual labour, Labour employed in small scale industry, Handloom/power-loom workers, Beedi and cigar workers, Employees in shops and commercial establishments, Sweepers and scavengers, Workers in tanneries, Tribal labour and Other unprotected labours.

Unorganised Sector in India: Report on conditions of work and promotion of livelihoods in the unorganised sector (2008) the unorganized sector is very vast and varied sector to confine within a conceptual definition. The National Commission for Enterprises defined the unorganized sector as "The unincorporated enterprises owned under proprietary or partnerships by the individuals or households to carry sale or production of goods and services employing less than ten workers. Rapaka Satya Raju (1989) this sector allow easy entry, micro operations, local ownership, labour intensive, usage of lower technologies, uncertain legal status, flexible pricing pattern and employment of high migrant workers. It lacks from sophisticated packing systems, brand name,

storage facility, distribution networks, financial aid and compensation mechanisms. Normally, it is very difficult to get the data of employment and income generation from the informal economy in the developing countries, but India estimated the informal sector by National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO). According to the NSSO report (2009-2010) out of 46.5 crore employed persons, 2.8 crore are from organised sector and rest 43.7 crore from unorganised sector. Among the total unorganized workers, 24.6 crore workers are employed in agricultural sector, 4.4 crore in construction, and rest are in manufacturing, trade, transport, communication and services activities. A large number of unorganised workers are home based workers engaging beedi rolling, agarbatti making, pappad making, tailoring, and embroidery work. Working conditions of unorganized labours can be achieved with better infrastructure, basic services, self help initiatives by linking workers and institutions providing services. Kishore C Samal (2013) the unorganized labour work for low wage, with more women workers, engaging family labour, home based works, instances of child labour, migrant workers, piece rate payment, contractual employment, recruitment through contractors, seasonal employments, under employment, casual works, self-employments, cooperatives for employees, not organized into trade unions, no much recourse to collective bargaining, hazardous job and debt bondage.

Economic Contribution to the Country: Mariappan K. (2011) in the era of Globalization and technology, the inability of the employer to expand employment in the formal sectors has increased reliance over unorganized sectors. According to National Statistical Commission (2012) informal sectors in the developing countries will contribute two third share of employment of the country. Indian economy rapidly grown in the last two decades with non-formal and dynamic employments boosting output and earnings. The higher economic growth can be achieved through inclusive growth the informal economy. According to 15th International Conference of Labour Statisticians (1993) The informal sector are producing goods or services primarily for generating employment and incomes to the poor". More than 90 per cent of the total workforce in the country and 50 per cent of the total Net National Product are contributed by the socially and economically underprivileged sections of the society working in informal sectors. Ruddar Datt (2008) ANCEUS Report (2005) among 458 million employed persons in India, 395 million i.e. 86 percent belong to unorganised sector. Rehman Sobhan (2010) informal sector contributes 50.6 per cent of Gross Domestic Product in the Country.

2. Problems of Unorganized Sector:

Kishore C Samal (2013) unorganised workers organize themselves to achieve a common object. The casual employment, ignorance, illiteracy, small establishments, low investments, scattered employment and superiority of the employer forbidden from being exclusive sector. It depends on organized sectors for its raw materials, capital, employment and marketing. The formal sector uses the model of sub contracting for engaging labour in the unorganized sector. Kulwant Rai Gupta (2009) problems of unorganized labours are multifarious in nature, hence confining this sector within a comprehensive framework is difficult. Changes in the trade and technology, global linkages are the threat to this sector. Employees has low job security, poor career growth, less leave and paid holidays, less protection against unfair trade practices. This sector is distinguished from formal sectors on the basis of deficiencies like seasonal employment, lack of employer-employee relationship and inadequate social security protection. Even though this sector contributes to the economy, an attempt is made to understand the vulnerability of this sector as under.

Insecurity in Job: Suresh Srivastava (1995) informal workers depends on multiple employments due to insecurity of work. Agricultural workers are engaged for only three months in a year and for the rest, they search an alternative job to sustain from starvation. National Commission for women reporting impact of WTO on Women in Agriculture (2005) they are engaged only few day's work in a year. National Commission for Enterprises in the unorganised Sector (2006) Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Workers Employment Guarantee Act, 2005 aims to provide employment guarantee for 100 days of work in the most backward districts of the country for manual labour. The factors like variations in the climate and location also affects the workers job security.

Occupational Hazards: Unorganised workers are exposed to hazardous working conditions which adversely affect their health. Health problem increase due to low nutrition and heavy physical labour. Low income and inability to pay for the health care leads the poor worker to be indebted. Studies reported that home based beedi workers are effected with respiratory and body ache due to inhalation of the tobacco dust and peculiar posture at work respectively. In fish processing units women are working in highly contaminated environment. In tobacco processing units, who involve in plucking, winnowing, grading and packing etc, the mist containing tiny particles of tobacco spread in the workplace enters the respiratory track and cause dangerous diseases like asthma, Tuberculosis etc. Salt Pan Workers suffer from severe eye problems due to the reflection of light from the heap of salt and skin diseases. Extensive usage of fertilizers, insecticides and pesticides also affect the health in the agriculture sector. Arjun Patel and Desai Kiran (1995) persons engage in applying, mixing and loading pesticides are exposed to toxic chemicals. Collecting statistics about accidents and injuries in farming need to be developed. The workers working in the fireworks, match works, leather tanning and construction are prone to accidents leading to amputations, due to unguarded operations or unsafe machines.

Inability to Secure Minimum Wages: In Peoples' Union for Democratic Rights v. Union of India (AIR 1982 SC 1473) The Supreme Court held that employing workers for wage below the statutory minimum level will result in forced labour, which is prohibited under Article 23 of the constitution of India even though poverty forces anyone to work for low wage. Studies on conditions of employment in the unorganized sector reported that daily wages are paid much below than the minimum fixed by the government. The casual workers are least protected due to low earnings. Wage is not influenced by the market forces. Report on the Working of The Minimum Wages Act, by Government of India (2013) lack of uniformity in wage structure is found across the states and union territories due to the application of the Minimum Wages Act only to the scheduled employments, in cases where the State Government fails to include particular employment within the scheduled list, are not covered under this legislation.

Lengthy working Hours: Arjun Patel and Desai Kiran (1995) long working hours beyond the regulatory norms will affect the social and family life, especially of women employees restraining them from participating in any cultural or social affairs of the family. Absence of laws to govern the working conditions of agricultural labour resulted for lengthy working hours. In Fireworks, Match works and hand loom work starts at early morning 6.00 a.m. and spreads for 12-15 hours per day. Kamala Kantha Mohabatra (2012) in many cases the statutory limit of working hours fixed for 48 hours per week, if violated instantly affects the working conditions of unorganised workers.

Poverty and Indebtedness: Kannan K.P (2012) workers are poor due to the low income and uncertain employments, facing problems to manage social and cultural life with poor economic status. Increased indebtedness in the agricultural sectors resulted in the increase of suicide of farmers.

Lack of Social Security Measures: Workers are economically inactive due to biological, personal, social and natural risks which are beyond human control. Biological risks covers modernity, sickness and old age, personal risks of widowhood and accident, social risks of unemployment, flood, fire, drought and closure need to be treated through social security mechanisms. The Social Insurance, should work as crisis intervention and help to resume back the lost employment due to uncertainty.

Lack of Health Security: 48 per cent of informal workers spend their Annual Household income for the Medical Care. The lack of Subsidy or Government support in health care has added vulnerability in their life. The inability to offer medical treatment have resulted poor health status. They are even driven towards poverty and indebtedness.

Poor Working Environment: Deficiencies in sanitation due to lack of washing facility, proper urinal and toilet facilities will affect the health of workers. Even the physical conditions like space, lighting, ventilation available are very poor compare to organized sectors.

Insecurity during Old Age: Leading life during the old age has become a challenge among unorganized workers. Construction workers and contract labours are not covered under the Provident Fund scheme. The nature of employment in Agriculture and Construction created a fear of displacement from work on age factor due to inability to work after certain age. The insecurity is due to lack of support from the family members, inadequate public health care facilities and expensive private health care for the aged.

Hazards Connected to Accidents: Accident cause damage to the health, loss in the earning capacity, requires additional expenditure for hospitalization and medical treatment. It cause partial or permanent disability from earning. Death of the bread winner will put the whole family to trouble, making them to be indebted by spending whole savings and assets.

Problems of Migrant Workers: Arjun Patel and Desai Kiran (1995) most migrant workers are poor, without adequate basic amenities, works under adverse environment. For example, the Sugarcane labourers, who lives in the open field, facing steady problems in the monsoon seasons from the menace of snakes, scorpions, mosquitoes etc. The workers harvesting the sugarcane crops do not have electricity, water supply and sanitation facility.

Low Bargaining Power: Gender and Economic Policy Discussion Forum (2012) the migrant workers have no right to bargain and works for less wage. Illiteracy, lack of awareness, lack of regulations and social isolation are the hurdles from unionizing. In spite of employment opportunities it generates and contributions to the Gross Domestic Product of the country, it lacks in the legal status affecting workers right prospects drastically. They cannot voice their demands or object the adverse attitude of the employers to protect their self interest.

Poor Employer-Employee Relationship: Rani Advani and Debi. SSaini (1995) scattered work culture without designated workplace, is preventing to build master-servant relationships to execute labour laws. The preference over multiple employers due to non availability of work and employment of home based workers through contractors has deprived the unorganised workers from getting minimum wages and social security.

Impact of Natural Disasters: Sudharshan, Canagarajha and S. V. Sethuraman (2001) natural disasters like flood, drought, famine, earth quake etc., will disturb the productivity affecting individual household income and asset of the unorganised workers.

Vulnerable Labour Segments: Migrant labours, bonded labours and child labours are the major vulnerable groups who are exploited and deprived in all spheres of life. Study group for construction of National

Commission on Labour (2005) reported that quarries, brick-kilns and construction sites engage bondage extending over generations through child labour. Vidyut Joshi (1995) creditor grant loan to labours, on agreement of forcing them to be under bondage till repayment of the sum forming debtor-creditor relationship. If the debtor could not repay the loan with specified interest, he shall serve the creditor for life. In bondage, exploitation exists due to the arbitrary terms and conditions vested upon the perpetuating debt and illegal detention. Ramadhar Giri (2007) Increasing demand for the workers in agriculture, the instances of bondage of the children of indebted labourers, who are forced to work in return for the debt. Bondage is common in carpet weaving, cloth printing, explosives, fireworks, cigarette making, printing and soldering jobs.

3. Legislative and Policy Framework:

Constitution of India: 'Labour' is a subject belong to 'Concurrent list' of Indian Constitution, with both Central and State Governments competent to enact legislations on the subject. The constitution grants some Fundamental Rights connecting to labour under Part III, by granting Right to Equality (Article 14-18). In *Devarajiah vs. Padmanna* (AIR 1961 Mad 35, 39) High Court held that Article 17 bans the practice of untouchability declaring it an offence punishable under law. Consequently, Parliament passed Untouchability (Offences) Act, 1955 declaring punishment for the offence. In 1976, the act was amended and renamed as Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955 with enhanced punishments. Protection of life and personal liberty (Article 21), Right against exploitation (Article 23) prohibiting Traffic in human beings, beggar and other forms of forced labour compelling anyone for involuntary and free service without wage or any forced labour which are punishable under law. In *Raj Bahadur vs. Legal Remembrancer* (AIR 1953 Cal, 522) it was held that Traffic in human beings is 'to deal in men and women like goods' either by selling or disposing or slavery which are punishable under Section 370 of Indian Penal Code, 1860. Right to Constitutional Remedies (Article 32) and Directive Principles of State Policy (Article 38- 51) in the Part IV, with a set of guiding principles for the governance of the country. Article 46 directs the State to promote educational and economic interest of the weaker sections to protect from social injustice and all forms of exploitation. Article 47 guides the State to raise the level of nutrition and the standard of living the people. Article 51(A)(e) ensures promotion of harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood among all the people of India and to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women.

The Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986: No child below the age of 14 years shall be employed or permitted to work in any specified employments under the act. Whoever employs in contravention to section 3 of the act shall be punishable with imprisonment for not be less than six months, extendable to two years, or with fine of not less than Rs. 20,000, extendable to Rs. 50,000 or with both. Many children are working in agriculture, handlooms, power looms, food industry, Beedi Industry, Small rubber and plastic factories, Jari (Golden Embroidery), domestic services, garages etc. Some are engaged as shoe shine boys, vendors, car cleaners, carriers in the trade of illicit liquor and other narcotic drugs. Children working in the Textile industry, engage in weaving. Work place being a small room, serves as home and workshop with less pay and could not attend school. Hotel employs children for housekeeping job just by paying Rs. 30 or Rs. 40 per day. Beedi industry engages children to close the ends of the beedies or tie thread round them.

International Initiatives: India is the signatory to the Treaty of Versailles and member of League of Nation and a permanent member of International Labour Organisation (ILO). It participates in the deliberations of ILO in the issues of policy making. Any member states within one year or within 18 months of closing of the session of the conference can put forth proposals for enacting legislations before the Director General for ratification. ILO is associated with the evolution of vocational training, Employees State Insurance Corporation, Central Labour Institute, National Labour Institute and Central Board for Workers Education, National Safety Council and National Productivity Council. The National Trade Unions like Indian National Trade Union Congress and Hindu Masdoor Sabha are assisted by the ILO in aiding family welfare, education and occupational safety. Protection against employment injury is enshrined in the preamble to ILO's constitution. 14 conventions and 13 recommendations have been adopted by ILO on health and safety covering accidents, safety, maximum weight, hygiene, safeguards against poisonous materials, welfare and housing. Working Environment Convention 1977 prevents, control and protect working environment from air pollution, noise and vibration. Murugan A.R (1997) ILO's code on Safety Regulations for Industrial establishments ensure safe working environment and health of the workers. Its conventions, recommendations and resolutions provide guidelines for the evolution of legislative and administrative measures to protect the interest of the labour. Press Information Bureau, Ministry of Labour & Employment, Government of India (16th July 2014) India ratified around 43 conventions, among which Four are fundamental human rights conventions viz., Forced Labour Convention (C-29), Equal Remuneration Convention (C-100), Abolition of Forced Labour Convention (C-105) and Discrimination (Employment & Occupation) Convention (C-111). The Ministry conducts regular meeting of the Committees on Convention (CoC), a tripartite working body to explore the possibility of ratification. India supported for the adoption of Social Protection Floors Recommendation (R-202) in 101st Session of the International Labour Conference held in Geneva in June, 2012 to protect the rights and welfare of all workers including unorganised sector.

Special Initiative: Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme and National Family Benefit Scheme are initiated by the Ministry of Rural Development. Janani Suraksha Yojana initiated by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Handloom Weavers' Comprehensive Welfare Scheme, Handicraft Artisans' Comprehensive Welfare Scheme and Pension to Master Craft Persons by the Ministry of Textiles, National Scheme for Welfare of Fishermen, Training and Extension by the Department of Animal Husbandry, Dairying & Fisheries, Janashree Bima Yojana and Aam Admi Bima Yojana by the Department of Financial Services. Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY) launched from 1st October, 2007 by the Ministry of Labour and Employment to provide Social Security measure since 1st April, 2008, by smart card based cashless health insurance for Rs. 30,000/- per annum to the BPL families specified by the Planning Commission in 75:25 ratio by the Centre and State Governments. For the States of north east region, Jammu & Kashmir in the ratio of 90:10. The scheme is active in 26 states and union territories benefitting 3,85,15,411 families including construction workers, licensed Railway Porters, Street Vendors, registered members of MGNREGA who worked more than fifteen days in the preceding financial year, Beedi Workers, Domestic Workers, Sanitation Workers, Mine Workers, Rickshaw Pullers, Rag Pickers and Auto/Taxi drivers.

National Policy on Skill Development: It is sponsored by the National Skill Development Corporation, a Non-profit company framed under the companies Act 1956. The Programme aims to achieve inclusive growth, usage of technology, higher productivity to raise the standard of the people. It creates opportunities for youth and women to acquire skills for their life. It encourages stakeholders to initiate skill development programmes, flexible delivery mechanisms, maintaining skilled workforce, entrepreneurship meeting market needs, coordinate the efforts of Central and State level agencies and empower public and private service providers. The policy includes institution based skill development using ITIs and ITCs, formal and informal apprenticeships, E-learning, distance learning, sector level learning adult learning, training to the retired or retiring employees, lifelong learning and Non formal training from the Civil Society Organizations.

National AIDS Policy 1997: The Government of India adopted this policy to prevent the spread of HIV infection through the collective efforts of Government and Non Government organizations. It aims to mobilize support of Non Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and Community Based Organisations (CBOs) to encourage community interventions to prevent the disease. It protects women, children and socially backward sections from vulnerability through Public Health Rationale to overcome the stigma and discrimination against the victims. It creates general awareness about the transmission and adoption of safe behavioural practices. It ensures health care in hospitals, homes care, research, vaccine in the country. Sudhir Varma, (2010) HIV/AIDS is a workplace issue affecting both workers and organisation in the public and private employments.

The Support for Training and Employment Programme (STEP) 1986-87: The National Commission for Self-employed women in the Informal Sector (1988) suggested protective measures by employment for income generation, minimum wages, welfare and support services, training and upgrading skills. It covers traditional sectors like Agriculture, small animal husbandry, dairying, fisheries, handlooms, handicrafts, khadi and village industries, sericulture, social forestry and waste land development. It is launched in 19 states, nearly 60% works in the dairy sector with 8,000 Women's Dairy Co-operatives benefitting more than 4 lakh members with the help of State Cooperative Milk Federations. Under the XI plan 1,60,560 beneficiaries were covered under the STEP scheme. This linked vocational courses under National Skill Development Programme to increase the employability of trained SHG members who are poor, asset less, marginalized women belonging to SC/ST households, women headed households and BPL families.

Design Development and Skill Up-Gradation: Handicraft items produced by the crafts person should meet the latest designs, aesthetics and competitive cost after considering the changing perceptions, likes and tasks of the customers through new designs and skill upgradation. National Minorities Development Finance Corporation (NMDFC) receive proposals from State channelizing agencies and NGOs through grants for Design Skill Development Training Programmes for the Minority Communities.

Schemes After 2000: The eleventh Five Year Plan initiated SABLA, for empowering adolescent girls, Indira Gandhi Matritva Sahyog Yojana (IGMSY) for Maternity Benefits, Mahila Kisan Sashaktikaran Pariyojana for women farmers, a scheme for leadership training for Minority women. National Mission for Empowerment of Women (NMEW) 2010 to facilitate Government Programmes. Around 16 States/UTs have established State Mission Authorities for Empowering Women and 11 States are setting up State Resource Centres for Women. Inclusion and mainstreaming of marginalized was specially emphasized under MGNREGA, Right to Free & Compulsory Education, National Rural Health Mission, National Rural Livelihood Mission and National Skill Development Mission. Gender Budgeting is initiated by the Department of Telecommunication under the Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas. Gender Responsive Budgeting is done by 56 Ministries through the Gender Budgeting Cells by scanning existing policies with public resources within a gender lens to reduce gender disparity. With revision of the guidelines of the scheme in 2009, Programme Implementation Manual was issued. Training for upgrading skills and credit facility is done by linking Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK), National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), and Council for Advancement of People's

Action and Rural Technology (CAPART) in agriculture, animal husbandry, dairying, fisheries, handlooms, handicrafts, Khadi and Village Industries, sericulture, waste land development and social forestry sectors.

Micro Units Development and Refinance Agency Bank (MUDRA Bank): For developing micro units, refinancing Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) for entrepreneurship and funding Non Corporate Small Business Sectors (NCSBS), Government of India constituted MUDRA Bank in India. MUDRA Yojana is in the 2016 Union Budget. It aims to refinance micro units with loan requirement of Rs. 50,000/- to Rs. 10,00,00,000/- lakhs and support MFIs for lending. The bank will refinance micro business under Pradhan Mantri MUDRA Yojana. The Bank has launched its three initiative products like SHISHU, KISHOR & TARUN to meet the funding needs of the micro units or entrepreneur. MUDRA will deliver the loan through NBFCs, MFIs, Rural Banks, District Banks, Nationalized Banks, Private Banks, Primary Lending Institutions and other intermediaries. MUDRA loan charges a base rate of interest between +1% to 7%. Any Indian citizen for engaging in manufacturing, processing, trading or service need credit of less than Rs. 10 lakh can approach Banks, MFIs, Financial Institutions or NBFC for availing MUDRA loans. MUDRA Bank is not refinancing agriculture sector under this scheme but traders of vegetables & fruits are covered. Central Government allotted an additional fund of One Lakh crore to this scheme and Rs. 40,000/- Crore for Mudra Bank Shishu Loan Scheme, Rs. 35,000/- Crore for Mudra Bank Kishor Loan Scheme and remaining Rs. 25,000/- Crore for Mudra Bank Tarun Loan Scheme.

The Unorganized Workers Social Security Act, 2008: It aims to provide social security and welfare for the unorganized workers. Central Government is empowered to make welfare schemes connected to life, disability, health, maternity and old age and the State Government for provident fund, employment injury, housing, education, skill up gradation, funeral and old age homes. These schemes are wholly funded by the Central or State Governments or partly from the beneficiary and employers. The Central Government constituted National Social Security Board and State Government constituted Social Security Board to recommend, monitor and review the expenditure of various schemes. Every unorganized workers, above 14 years, will register within the act shall be issued with an identity card and are eligible for social security benefits under the scheme. It covers schemes like National Family Benefit Scheme, Janani Suraksha Yojna, Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme and Aam Admi Bima Yojna etc.

4. Conclusion:

Sudharshan, Canagarajha and S. V. Sethuraman (2001) India do not have a specific scheme to register whole workers of unorganised sector. The wage payment by the owner, sub contractor, agent and middlemen are violating wage regulations causing miseries to the marginalized workers. Employment on sub-contract, have evaded welfare standards specified by the law. Non compliance of labour regulation relating to minimum wage, social security and welfare have increased miseries of informal sector. Lack of skills and training, home based work, micro enterprises, has created unregulated work environment. Non availability of jobs in the capital intensive organized sectors due technological advancement encourage employments in the labour intensive unorganized sectors. Many are attracted to the unorganised sector due to the easy employment and income. Government should regulate informal economic activities with safety and health. The causes for injuries, fatalities, diseases, disasters in this sector should be controlled. The enterprises should focus to contribute to the national assets by creating community awareness on sensitive issues connected to workers. Attention should be provided to encourage green jobs, sustainable development, community participation, health and safety consciousness and enriching the skills of unorganised workers in India.

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